

Monitoring Researchers' Open Science Practices in Education

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ABSTRACT

Keywords

measuring open science, questionnaire, attitudes

Purpose of this paper

Open Science is a movement permeating disciplinary boundaries with the goal of improving scientific conduct by sharing processes with a wider audience (cf. Fecher & Friesike, 2014). For example, van der Zee and Reich (2018) describe for the case of education science, that open science addresses replicability problems, like costs of accessing research articles, the selective reporting of studies with statistically significant results, or the so called *researchers degree of freedom* in conducting studies in a way that they have desired results. Against this background, Open Science seems to be a desirable goal to move to.

To be able to study how researchers can be motivated to actually do open science, it is necessary to quantify their endorsement of open science. A quantitative conceptualization of the adoption of open science practices allows to compare causes for open science, makes it possible to show how the adoption of open science practices develops over time, and allows to study open science practices as predictor for further outcomes, for example for successful grant proposals.

The goal of the current project is to monitor the use of open scientific practices in education science in Germany. Therefore, we developed a theoretically derived questionnaire with the goal to assess the degree to which a broad range of open scientific practices are done, which we refer to as *scientific openness*. This questionnaire will be used in a large sample of educational researchers in Germany. We will relate individuals' scientific openness to disciplinary backgrounds, scientific approaches, as well as attitudes towards scientific norms and open

science. The project aims to answer three questions: (a) How *open* is education science in Germany, (b) which constructs are associated with scientific openness on the individual level, and (c) which constructs are associated with scientific openness on the contextual level?

The development of the questionnaire is based on contemporary definitions of open science. These are summarized by Bosman and Cramer (2017). Definitions share some core aspects, but diverge in other aspects. As a working definition, we refer to *open science* as a facet of the broader concept of *open knowledge* (which further summarizes *open educational resources*, *open source software* and *open hardware*). Open science are scientific behaviors and practices that make science more (a) open to participation to the broad scientific community and the public, as well as (b) open to use, check, modify, re-use and redistribute scientific products like data, code, notes, or research reports.

Design/methodology/approach

Based on this definition, we derived a core set of eleven open scientific practices. These scientific practices are based on research cycles as presented by Open Science and Research Initiative (2014), Bosman & Cramer (2016), or the Center for Open Science (n.d.). This core set included for example practices like *sharing data*, *publishing open access papers*, *sharing research notes*, or *disseminating research results for the public via social media*. To quantify the degree of scientific openness, we chose a response scale that resulted in a higher scientific openness when practices were made open to a larger audience (cf. Fecher, Friesike, & Helbing, 2015). For example, sharing data freely with the public would result in a numerically higher score in scientific openness than sharing data (exclusively) with colleagues in the same institution.

To understand reasons for scientific openness, we included a number of potential predictors in the questionnaire based on previous research (Kim & Stanton, 2016; Fecher, Friesike, Helbing, & Linek, 2017). These include academic disciplines, disciplinary attitudes and attitudes towards open science. Because of the conceptual similarity to scientific openness, the endorsement of Mertonian norms is also considered (Anderson, 2010).

To evaluate the applicability of the questionnaire, we will first check the questionnaire in a qualitative pretest. We will use a small sample of educational researchers with diverse disciplinary and methodological backgrounds. The sample will work on the questionnaire and thereby produce think-aloud protocols. Following, they will be interviewed for their

understanding of the questionnaire. Based on results of this procedure, the questionnaire will be iteratively adapted.

In the main part of the project, the questionnaire will be used in a large sample of educational researchers throughout Germany. We will aim for a sample that is as large as possible. To achieve a high number of participants, we will contact disciplinary associations and use their mailing lists. Furthermore, participants are offered an individual openness profile as feedback.

Expected Findings

The main result will be an estimate of the level of open science for the German educational sciences. Furthermore associations between scientific openness and attitudes toward science and open sciences provide potential explanations for researchers' engagement in open science.

Limitations

Due to the quantitative nature of the investigations, open science practices will be investigated in a closed format. This approach makes it necessary to limit open science practices to a specific set and also to limit response options to a specific set. The selection of practices and response options may not adequately represents all ways in which researchers engage in open science. A similar limitation is true for attitudes toward science and open science, where researchers need to stick to possible answering options.

Furthermore, the study will be cross-sectional. This design precludes the interpretation of the employed predictors as explanations for scientific openness without further assumptions.

Practical implications

Results provide a first orientation of how open the education science in Germany is. This evaluation can serve as a source for information regarding the development and demands for scientific infrastructures as well as policy considerations.

What is original/value of the paper

A central contribution of the project is to provide a questionnaire to assess scientific openness. This measure can be adopted by a wide range of social sciences with similar methodologies as education science. Quantifying scientific openness makes it possible to study its predictors,

consequences, and development over time. Furthermore, the questionnaire allows investigations on both the individual as well as on a disciplinary level.

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